

Synthesis and characterization of Pr and Nb doped ZnO by spray pyrolysis technique

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Abstract

Zinc oxide (ZnO) is a n-type semiconductor material which has a wide direct band gap of energy ~ 3 eV. Dopant in ZnO nanostructures is an effective way to improve ZnO's structural properties in various applications. In the present study Pr and Nb doped ZnO were synthesized on glass substrate by using chemical spray pyrolysis at 450°C temperature. The concentration of impurities is varied from (0% to 4 mol %) for (Pr-ZnO) and (1% to 4 mol%) for (Nb-ZnO). The synthesized thin films are characterized by X-Ray diffraction, which shows hexagonal structure with 57nm crystalline size for optimized concentration of Pr and it is indexed using JCPDS card number (01-079-0206) and for Nb doped ZnO JCPDS card number (01-079- 0208). Due to their excellent optical and electrical properties prepared films are used as a transparent window layer and electrodes in solar cell.

Keyword: ZnO, Pr, Nb, Structural and Optical properties, Chemical Spray Pyrolysis.

Introduction

There has been great interest in the oxide semiconductor and its ternary alloys in recent years for its various application [1]. In present paper we deposit ZnO material doped with Pr and Nb at various concentration by using spray pyrolysis technique [2-7]. Spray pyrolysis is a well-established and widely used technique for the film processing. Basically, pyrolysis is a chemical reaction. The spray deposition based on the mechanical transformation of the solution to droplets steam by using compressed gas or ultrasonic waves. Among the various chemical methods solution spraying technique is the most popular today because its applicability to produce variety of conducting and semiconducting materials [8-10].

ZnO is known to be one kind of the important photocatalysts because of its unique advantage, such as its low price, high photocatalytic activity and nontoxicity, that has attracted a great deal of attention. Zinc oxide is a n- type semiconductor which has a wide and direct band gap energy of ~3.3eV at room temperature [11]. ZnO can be used for some application such as electronics, optoelectronics [12], sensors [13], photonic devices and photocatalyst [14]. ZnO nanostructures were deposited by using various technique such as Vapour phase deposition [15], Pulsed laser deposition [16], Thermal evaporation [17], sol-gel [18], Hydrothermal method [19], Chemical bath deposition [20] and Spray pyrolysis technique [21]. Doping of ZnO nanostructures is one effective way to improve the structural properties of ZnO for various applications. In particular, doping ZnO with rare earth materials is of interest in tailoring its optical properties. In this work, we synthesized and characterized the undoped ZnO and Pr also Nb doped ZnO on glass substrate by using spray pyrolysis technique and then investigated optical and morphological properties. The spray pyrolysis technique has many advantages such as low cost, deposition equipment that is simple and easy fabrication of large area films. Precursor solution is sprayed through by nozzle above the surface of substrate which has been heated.

Methodology

Nanocrystalline ZnO thin films were deposited on glass substrate by Spray Pyrolysis method. The substrate was very carefully cleaned using chromic acid, Substrate were boiled at 60°C temperature. When temperature reaches towards room temperature removed the glass slides from chromic acid and then washed with distilled water, after that before deposition substrate were cleaned ultrasonically. After cleaning with acetone, substrate was allowed to heat at high temperature (450°C). (0.1M) of zinc acetate ($ZnCH_3COOH$) were diluted with (35ml) of distilled water, (60ml) methanol and (5ml) acetic acid. Deposition rate required up to (1-2

min.). Then dopant material of Pr (Praseodymium Oxide) of (0.1M) diluted in 25ml of solution (5 ml Nitric acid (HNO_3) + 20 ml distilled water). The distance maintained between spraying nozzle and hot plate is about 39cm. The dopant material was deposited at various concentration.

[In similar manner, Niobium was also doped in ZnO at various concentration. Synthesized pure ZnO and Niobium-doped ZnO (Nb-ZnO) nanoparticles containing (1% to 4 mol%) Nb. ZnO and Nb doped ZnO were synthesized on glass substrate by using chemical spray pyrolysis at 450°C temperature.

Result and Discussion

1. XRD STUDIES:

Fig. 1 represents the x-ray diffractogram of the ZnO films. From XRD data, it is seen that the films exhibit hexagonal (wurtzite) crystal structure with preferential growth along the (002) plane [24]. For both optimized sample the intensity of the (002) diffraction is highest at the substrate temperature of 450°C, indicating an improvement of the crystallinity at this temperature. All the peaks in the diffraction pattern were indexed on the basis of a JCPDS data card No. (01-079-0206) and JCPDS card number (01-079- 0208). The crystalline size if the ZnO thin films prepared at different concentration was evaluated from full width at half maxima (FWHM) of (002) peak using Scherrer's formula [25]. The grain size obtain for the optimized concentration (2%Pr) is 57 nm and for (4% Nb) is 15nm. It was observed that the grain size values increase with increasing concentration and decreases with decreasing concentration.

$$D = \frac{0.94\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

Where λ : X- ray wavelength
 θ : Bragg diffraction angle
 β : FWHM

2. Optical absorption studies

For the direct transition, the optical band gap energy of undoped ZnO and doped ZnO was determined by using the equation [22],

Fig (a) Pr doped ZnO

Fig (b) Nb doped ZnO

Thin film	Un-doped ZnO	ZnO: Pr1%	ZnO: Pr2%	ZnO: Pr3%	ZnO: Pr4%	ZnO: Pr5%	ZnO: Pr6%
Band gap(ev)	3.2538	3.2163	3.2087	3.7727	3.7816	3.7912	3.8024
Thin film	Un-doped ZnO	ZnO:Nb1%	ZnO:Nb2%	ZnO:Nb3%	ZnO:Nb4%	ZnO: Nb5%	ZnO:Nb6%
Band gap (ev)	3.2538	3.2454	3.2407	3.2404	3.2385	3.3224	3.3263

Fig. 3 UV-Vis Spectra for optimised 2 % Pr doped ZnO & 4 % Nb doped ZnO

$$\alpha = \text{Const.} \frac{(\hbar\nu - E_g)^{1/2}}{\hbar\nu} \text{-----(2)}$$

Where $\hbar\nu$ is the photon energy and E_g is the optical band gap which could be calculated from $(\alpha\hbar\nu)^2$ versus $\hbar\nu$ plot, which are shown in figure. By extrapolating the linear part of plot to $\alpha = 0$, optical band gap was estimated. From Fig., it is observed that as concentration rate increases, band gap increases, it becomes maximum (3.9712eV) at temperature 450°C.

Optical spectra of undoped ZnO and doped ZnO are shown in following figure. The value of E_g so obtained which vary from (3.1to 3.9eV) which indicate the variation of band gap with increasing molar concentration of Pr [23].

Optimized condition of Pr doped ZnO is at 2% and bandgap of this sample is 3.2087 eV. Similarly, optimized condition of Nb doped ZnO is at 4% and bandgap of this sample is 3.2385 eV.

3. FTIR SPECTRA:

FTIR spectra of pure ZnO, Nb-doped ZnO and Pr-doped ZnO photocatalyst are measured to identify the functional group. The absorption peak of ZnO is found at 510 cm^{-1} . The weak stretching C-O bond is found at 1100 cm^{-1} [26]. As doping concentration goes on increasing there is observed that curve becomes flatter, which shows that doping of Pr and Nb elements in ZnO is successfully done. No any other impurities are found in sample, so there is no other functional group is present in sample.

Fig. FTIR analysis

Fig (a) Pure ZnO

Fig (b) Nb doped ZnO at 4%

Fig (c) Pr doped ZnO at 2%

4. Morphological Properties:

To study the surface morphological properties of prepared films they were characterized by Scanning electron microscope at same magnification. It clearly shows the impact of doping concentration on deposited films. Images are shown in following figure. SEM images of pure ZnO showed rough surface topography with tiny grains distributed over the smooth background. For optimized concentration of Pr Doped ZnO and Nb doped ZnO SEM images are shown in following figure.

Conclusions

The dopant thin film of Pr and Nb - ZnO were successfully deposited by a spray pyrolysis technique. The films were deposited onto glass substrate at 450°C temperature. Substrate temperature during deposition was found to have Influenced the phase. The films have good optical quality properties. The optical energy gap is varied from (3.1 to 3.9 eV) for varied concentration. The synthesized thin films are characterized by X-Ray diffraction method which shows hexagonal structure for optimized concentration of (2% Pr) with 57nm crystalline size and it optimized by JCPDS card number (01-079-0206). Similarly, for Nb X-Ray diffraction method which shows hexagonal structure for optimized concentration of (4% Nb) with 15 nm crystalline size and it optimized by JCPDS card number (01-079- 0208).

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References

1. Md. Atikur Rahman, A Review on Semiconductors Including Applications and Temperature Effects in Semiconductors, American Scientific Research Journal for Engineering, Technology, and Sciences (ASRJETS) (2014) Volume 7, No 1, pp 50-70
2. Z. Sofiani, B. Derkowska, P. Dalasinski, Z. Lukasiak, K. B Artkiewicz, W. Bala, M. Addou, A. Lamrani Mehdi, L. Dghughi, I.V. Kityk and B. Sahraoui. Growth of ZnO: Ce layers by spray pyrolysis method for nonlinear optical studies.
3. N. Aisah, D. Gustiono, V. Fauzia, I. Sugihartono and R. Nuryad Synthesis and enhanced photocatalytic activity of Ce-Doped Zinc Oxide nanorods by Hydrothermal method.
4. N. Wenbin, L. Xianglin, S. Karuturi, D. Fam, H. Fan, S. Shrestha, L. wong and A. Yoong Tok. Application of atomic layer deposition in solar cells.
5. V. Gokulakrishan, S. Parthiban, K. Jeganathan, K. Ramamurthi. Structural, Optical and electrical properties of Nb- doped ZnO Thin films prepared by spray pyrolysis method.
6. S. Aznar- Cervantes, M. Alistle, I. Garrido, J. Maria Yanez-Gascon, N. Vela, L. Cenis, S. Navarro and J. Fenoll, Electrospun silk fibroin/TiO₂ mats, preparation, characterization and efficiency for the photocatalytic solar treatment of pesticide polluted water.
7. G. Turgut, E. Keskenler, A. Serdar, S. Erdal, S. Dog, D. Bahattin, Effect of Nb doping on structural, electrical and optical properties of spray deposited SnO₂ thin films

- Mehmet Ertugrul d G. Turgut et al. / Superlattices and Microstructures 56 (2013) 107–116
8. D. Daksh and Y. Agrawal, Rare Earth-Doped Zinc Oxide Nanostructures: A Review Rev. Nanosci. Nanotechnol. 2016, Vol. 5, No. 1 2157-9369/2016/5/001/027 doi:10.1166/rnn.2016.1071
 9. D. Perednis & L. Gauckler Thin Film Deposition Using Spray Pyrolysis Journal of Electroceramics, 14, 103–111, 2005 C 2005 Springer Science Business Media, Inc. Manufactured in The Netherlands.
 10. A. Mandal, S. Katuwa, F. Tettey, A. Gupta, S. Bhattarai, S. Jaisi, D. Bhandari, A. Shah, N. Bhattarai, and N. Parajuli Current Research on Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles: Synthesis, Characterization, and Biomedical Application Nanomaterials 2022, 12, 3066. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12173066>
 11. S. Abdullahi, M. Momoh, A.U Moreh, A.M. Bayawa, M. B. Abdullahi Comparative Studies on Thin Film of Zinc Oxide (ZnO) Deposited by Spray Pyrolysis and RF Sputtering Technique. Scholars Journal of Engineering and Technology (SJET) ISSN 2321-435X (Online) Sch. J. Eng. Tech., 2017; 5(7):365-372 ISSN 2347-9523
 12. J. Caia, Z. Mac, U. Wejinyaa, M. Zoua, Y. Liud, H Zhouc, and X. Menga, A Revisit to Atomic Layer Deposition of Zinc Oxide Using Diethylzinc and Water as Precursors
 13. Y. Ammaih, A. Bouchaib, A. Ridah, P. Thevenin, M. Siadat Structural, optical and electrical properties of ZnO:Al thin films for optoelectronic applications Received: 18 March 2013 / Accepted: 16 August 2013 / Published online: 4 September 2013 © The Author(s) 2013. This article is published with open access at Springerlink.com
 14. X. Wang Touch Sensor Application of Spray Deposited ZnO Films All content following this page was uploaded on 23 November 2017. DOI: 10.1109/ISIE.2017.8001452
 15. M. Islam, M. Rahman, S. Farhad, J. Podder Structural, optical and photocatalysis properties of sol-gel deposited Al-doped ZnO thin films PII: S2468-0230(19)30086-0 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2019.05.007>
 16. Z. Chen, K. Shum, T. Salagaj, W. Zhang, and K. Strobl ZnO Thin Films Synthesized by Chemical Vapor Deposition, NY 11210 Conference Paper · June 2010 DOI: 10.1109/LISAT.2010.5478331 ·Source: IEEE Xplore
 17. M. Tsoutsouva¹, C. Panagopoulos, D. Papadimitriou, I. Fasaki, M. Kompitsas, N. Galanis, D. Manolagos ZnO Thin Films Prepared by Pulsed Laser Deposition All content following this page was uploaded by Michael Kompitsas on 29 October 2019
 18. N. Guermat and W. Daranf Laboratoire d'Analyse des Signaux et Systèmes (LASS), Faculté de Technologie, Université Mohamed Boudiaf -M'sila, M'sila Structural and Optical Properties of ZnO Thin Films Prepared by Thermal Evaporation, Algerie. e-mail: noubeil.guermat@univ-msila.dz Laboratory of thin films and Interface (LCMI), University of Constantine 1, Constantine, Algeria.
 19. V. Anand, S. Sood and A. Sharma Characterization of ZnO Thin Film Deposited by Sol-Gel Process Cite as: AIP Conference Proceedings 1324, 399 (2010); <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3526243>.
 20. J. Shim, H. Chang, and S. Kim Research Article Rapid Hydrothermal Synthesis of Zinc Oxide Nanowires by Annealing Methods on Seed Layers Hindawi Publishing Corporation Journal of Nanomaterials Volume 2011, Article ID 582764, 6 pages doi:10.1155/2011/582764
 21. A. A. Surse¹, H. J. Kardile², A. A. Pandit³, 239 Synthesis and Characteristics of Pure ZnO Thin Films Prepared by Chemical Bath Deposition Method IARJSET ISSN (Online) 2393-8021 ISSN (Print) 2394-1588 International Advanced Research Journal in Science, Engineering and Technology ISO 3297:2007 Certified Vol. 4, Issue 11, November 2017 Copyright to IARJSET DOI 10.17148/IARJSET.2017.41134
 22. M. Andrzej, S. Piotr, K. Marian, P. Volodymyr Zinc oxide films prepared by spray EPJ Web of Conferences 133, 03004 (2017) DOI: 10.1051/713303004 IC Se NOB 2016
 23. M. Toma, O. Selyshchev, Y. Havryliuk, A. Pop, D. Zahn, Optical and Structural Characteristics of Rare Earth-Doped ZnO Nanocrystals Prepared in Colloidal Solution. Photochem 2022, 2, 515–527. <https://doi.org/10.3390/photochem2030036>
 24. M. Taskin and J. Podder Study the Effect of Molar Concentration on the Optical and Surface Properties of ZnO Thin Films Prepared by Spray Pyrolysis Applied Science Reports www.pscipub.com/ ASR E-ISSN: 2310-9440 / P-ISSN: 2311-0139 DOI: 10.15192/PSCP.ASR.2014.3.3.109111
 25. Amalraj, G. Senguttuvan Effect of Solution Molarity on the Structural, Morphological and Optical Properties of Nanostructured Zinc Oxide Thin Films ISSN: 0974-2115 www.jchps.com Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences April - June 2017 867 JCPS.
 26. Monshi, M. Foroughi, M. Monshi Modified Scherrer Equation to Estimate More Accurately Nano-Crystallite Size Using XRD World Journal of Nano Science and Engineering, 2012, 2, 154-160 <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/wjnse.2012.23020> Published Online September 2012.